

Original Research Article

Reflexive Expertise: Mathematics Teacher Educators' Development through Collaborative Autoethnography

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ABSTRACT: This collaborative autoethnographic project explores reflexive expertise, conceptualized as the ability to move across and beyond paradigms, and the ways in which it supports mathematics teacher educators in navigating the complexities of teaching culturally relevant and responsive pedagogy to preservice teachers. In parallel with the design, implementation, and revision of culturally relevant mathematics activities, we engaged in ongoing critical self-reflection. We share data from three conversations that highlight how we reflexively shift across paradigms. In the first, we struggled to code preservice teachers' ideas about culture. In the second, we attempted to contextualize education as a profession in the wake of the tragic school shooting in Uvalde, TX. In the third, we questioned pedagogical assumptions, particularly the illusion of safe spaces in educational settings. We faced several tensions and impasses—aporias—that resulted in paradigmatic shifts and revealed hidden biases and assumptions. We posit that reflexive expertise is another method to explore researcher positioning, particularly for researchers with privilege. Reflexive expertise has transformative potential, especially in concert with collaborative autoethnography, which we suggest as a powerful methodology for developing the expertise of fellow mathematics teacher educators.

KEYWORDS: collaborative autoethnography, reflexivity, expertise, positioning

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The ways we develop, refine, and enact our expertise as mathematics teacher educators (MTEs) are influenced by our beliefs, experiences, and contexts. Our work as MTEs requires us to prepare preservice teachers and support inservice teachers across a wide range of knowledge and skills. The Association of Mathematics Teacher Educators has repeatedly emphasized the importance of preparing teachers to challenge inequity in mathematics education (AMTE, 2020, 2017, 2015). The National Council of Teachers of Mathematics has also explicitly supported and offered guidance to teachers around how to teach mathematics in equitable ways (e.g. NCTM, 2014) and have published position statements on access and equity (NCTM, 2014), building positive mathematical identities in all students (NCTM, 2016), and interrogating how practices and policies can be transformed to help multilingual learners thrive (NCTM, 2022). The nature of equity work requires MTEs to develop activities and teach about equitable teaching practices that draw on the lived experiences and cultures of their preservice teachers. Further, the broader sociopolitical landscape, such as recent reforms and policy changes that target higher education, require MTEs to enact curriculum amongst tensions that require negotiation and reflection. In other words, the expertise required by MTEs to support preservice and inservice teachers to teach mathematics in equitable ways includes characteristics that extend beyond mathematical content and pedagogical knowledge.

Researchers of expertise have spanned several theoretical paradigms. Those studying cognitive expertise have explored the attributes and characteristics of highly-skilled individuals. Researchers studying sociocultural expertise have explored characteristics of communities of practice as and within systems (Chi, 2011; Reimann & Markauskaite, 2018), such as a group of mathematics teacher educators (MTEs) operating in cultural and political systems (Brown, Collins, and Duguid, 1989). Others have combined cognitive and sociocultural framings (Danish & Gresalfi, 2018). We posit that reflexivity, which involves “reflecting upon and acknowledging one’s positions, involvements, and subjectivities” (Chan, 2017, p. 31) is one lens through which MTEs can come to understand their own expertise. By centering this conception of reflexivity, we were able to, as a collective of MTEs, interrogate our own culture, the ways we teach about culture, and in turn, develop our expertise as MTEs. While most researchers’ ideas of reflexivity orient on their static position in research (e.g. Milner, 2007), in this manuscript, we draw on Holland’s (1999) conceptualization of reflexivity through an autoethnographic analysis (Chang, 2008) to explore how our professional conversations shift or span across paradigms, what we call *orientations*, as our positioning shifts as MTEs (Boveda & Annamma, 2023). In doing so, the framing of our work necessarily shifts. We describe this active positioning and repositioning as *reflexive expertise*.

We contextualize this manuscript in our multi-year project to develop and enact lessons about culturally relevant mathematics for undergraduate preservice teachers. During this project, we found that our research group worked in ways which were unique from all the other research spaces we worked in. This article shares our methodology and research group dynamics as an offering to the field by investigating the following research question: *In what ways do a group of MTEs demonstrate reflexive expertise as they engage in the context of culturally relevant mathematics teaching with PTs in their courses?*

Theoretical Framework

In this section, we point the reader to a singular concept that informs how we conceptualize reflexive expertise: movement. In the process of examining the unique components of our collaboration, movement arose as a unifying theme as we engaged in the various professional practices of MTEs.

Positioning, Paradigms, and Reflexivity

In our collaboration, we consider our roles as MTEs and researchers and the power these roles bestow. This power extends across discursive practices involving race (Martin, 2009; Milner, 2007), culture (Ladson-Billings, 1995; Ladson-Billings & Tate, 1995), gender, ableism (Lambert & Tan, 2017), class, and their multiple intersections (Crenshaw, 1989, 1991; Dillard, 2000; Freire, 1993; Leyva, 2017). The implications of power are both visible and invisible (Bullock, 2018; Milner, 2007), and as MTEs, we proceed with care as we engage in research. One potential path made available for us as researchers is through positionality statements, the act of documenting one's identities, group memberships, and world views, thereby attempting to make transparent the potential biases that result from one's position. Milner (2007) highlights the need for researcher positionality when doing work in racialized and cultured spaces. Over the intervening years, other researchers have provided processes for establishing one's positionality. For example, Jacobson and Mustafa (2019) provide a graphic organizer as a road map to identify tiers of positionality. Secules et al. (2021) identify six dimensions of positionality and associated prompts for reflection: research questions, epistemology, ontology, methodology, researcher-as-instrument, and communication. Recently, Boveda and Annamma (2023) contend that positionality statements imply a static stance, hiding potential interactions and effects of power. Instead, drawing on the concept of *positioning* (Harré, 2012; Harré & Davies, 1990; Harré & van Langenhove, 1999) they offer an intersectional framework for researchers to consider their positioning, as a dynamic and discursive process, amongst systems of oppression. Research positionality and positioning share two common components: the knowledge production process and reflexivity as a tool to illuminate researcher positioning in that process.

Paradigms in Mathematics Education

In the knowledge production process, researchers are often trained to identify their ontological and epistemological perspectives, our ways of being and ways of knowing in this world. These perspectives inform the theoretical underpinnings of our work (Bogdan & Biklen, 2007), called paradigms, as “a loose collection of logically related assumptions, concepts, or positions that orient thinking and research” (p. 24). Paradigms encompass: our view of reality (one world or many, objective or subjective); our view of truth (one truth or many, politicized or socially constructed); how we approach questioning in our research; and how we approach the methodological process of our research (Lather, 2006). Such paradigms can be broadly categorized as Positivism, Interpretivism, Critical Theories, and Deconstructivism, and a researcher's knowledge production process can span multiple categories, depending on their beliefs and goals. Paradigms are not static constructs. Rather, they are researcher perspectives informed by the historical evolution of the field, in this case mathematics education.

Stinson and Bullock (2012) conceptualized researcher paradigms as moments to illuminate the “possibilities and impossibilities” of mathematics education research. Moments are not discrete spaces, nor did the field progress through the moments as stepping-stones. Rather the moments are “distinct yet overlapping and simultaneously operating” (p. 43). These moments include the process-product moment, the interpretivist moment, the sociocultural moment, and the sociopolitical moment. Beginning in the 1970s, mathematics education researchers ushered the process-product moment, seeking to quantify the effects of classroom practice with student outcomes. In this moment, positivism and post-positivism are the paradigms of choice, and researchers seek to predict phenomena through quantitative methodologies. In the late 1970s, the interpretivist-constructivist moment shifted towards qualitative methodologies and the interpretivism and constructivism paradigms. The aim shifted from predicting social phenomena to understanding it, exploring meaning-making and interactions within the classroom. In the mid-

1980s, the social turn (Lerman, 2000) signified researchers' acknowledgement that social activity occurred in context. This moment explores teaching and learning through sociocultural and sociohistorical lenses. The sociopolitical turn (Gutiérrez, 2013) occurred as researchers shifted toward critical paradigms that offered perspectives on the interactions between knowledge, power, and identity in teaching and learning. This moment explores issues of equity and inequity in teaching and learning, questioning why math and for whom. Finally, acknowledging the historicized framing of Stinson and Bullock (2012), Gutiérrez's (2022) *A Spiritual Turn: Toward Desire-Based Research and Indigenous Futurity in Mathematics Education* signaled a new moment, one where mathematics education researchers "see unity in all things and draw on tradition to heal and remake ourselves" (p. 381), extending to paradigms that encompass the spirit in addition to mind, body, context, and power. Other turns in mathematics education exist (e.g. Larnell & Bullock, 2018), but for the purposes of this manuscript, we limit our conceptions to these five moments.

Each moment offers different affordances and constraints as they are paradigms of research, shaping how we as researchers view and approach our work. In other words, the moments underscore ontological and epistemological perspectives that inform mathematics education research in the present. In this manuscript, we conceptualize Stinson and Bullock's (2012) moments as MTE *orientations*. We do not argue that one *orientation* stands above another or that MTEs and researchers should adopt specific *orientations* to, for example, negotiate underlying biases that are inherent to our choices as researchers in our epistemological and ontological perspectives (Scheurich & Young, 1997). Nor do we argue for an eclectic mix of *orientations* (Lather, 2006; Stinson & Bullock, 2012) in an attempt to find a single *orientation* that aligns with our epistemological, ontological, and axiological perspectives. Rather, we embrace the ephemeral quality that the name *orientations* implies, that researchers intentionally and unintentionally shift between paradigms as we encounter, explore, and negotiate tensions in our work. As MTEs and researchers, making these choices and underlying theoretical framings visible offers opportunities to reckon with the seemingly hidden dangers pervasive in our understandings (Bullock, 2018; Milner, 2007). In other words, we argue that not only is a researcher's positioning fluid (Boveda & Annamma, 2023), researchers should intentionally shift their perspectives—their *orientations*—through a reflexive process.

Reflexivity as Movement

Reflexivity is a process of reflecting and acknowledging subjectivities, biases, and positions in the research process (Chan, 2017; Holland, 1999; Milner, 2007). In other words, reflexivity offers one way for researchers to understand themselves and the resulting effects of their presence on the research process. For some, such a process is intended to uncover racial, cultural, gendered, abled, and other forms of researcher bias (Boveda & Annamma, 2023; Jacobson & Mustafa, 2019; Milner, 2007; Secules et al., 2021). Such definitions of reflexivity undoubtedly align with critical disciplinary theories; however, we adopt Holland's (1999) framing of reflexivity to capture movement.

Holland's (1999) conceptualization of reflexivity extends across varying levels of complexity and depth. On the most basic level, it is self-contained, the type of reflexivity that feels most static, within a single *orientation*. As reflexivity expands, it considers contrasting viewpoints, the impact one research paradigm has on another and their interplay, such as the affordances and constraints two *orientations* might offer (e.g. Danish & Gresalfi's 2018 synthesis of the cognitive and sociocultural). Alternatively, reflexivity can adopt an eclectic approach to *orientations*, combining pieces of multiple paradigms to curtail weaknesses and maximize strengths (Stinson & Bullock, 2012). Reflexivity can also capture movement, positioning individual processes within larger

systems. Finally, reflexivity can acknowledge that *orientations* are human constructs, that they carry an agenda, personal and cultural (i.e. Scheurich & Young, 1997). In this level, reflexivity is radical, bound by no paradigm, with the goal to move past the constraints of an individual orientation,

...As a method of evaluating existing systems of knowledge, tied in as they are to sectional interests and constellations of power. It invites re-entry into the epistemological and sectional complexities of our human condition to intervene, “knowingly” according to our ethical priorities (Holland, 1999, p. 476).

This type of reflexivity resonates with dialectical reasoning (Freire, 1993; Mao & Knight, 1990), where, through praxis, one seeks to transcend existing tensions within and across individual *orientations*. This type of reflexivity falls at the intersection of Scheurich & Young’s (1997) critique of the inherent racialized biases of paradigms, Boveda & Annamma’s (2023) critique of the static nature of positionality, and Gutiérrez’s (2022) call to turn mathematics education towards the ethical and towards healing. Indeed, when mathematics teacher educators and education researchers enact movement across and beyond paradigms in the process of their work, they exhibit reflexive expertise.

Aporias. MTEs can actively engage in reflexive expertise, in movement of their *orientations* to their work, when they contend with logical and practical contradictions in the epistemological and ontological assumptions brought by their current orientation. Lather (2006) conceptualizes these contradictions as aporias, as impasses, as “the stuck place of social research” (p.48). An aporia can be encountered when the social and political realities of our field or position are unresolvable with our goals or values. For example, a common narrative encountered in teacher preparation programs is the goal to create safe spaces in classrooms. However, this goal is contextualized within the stark reality of education since 1999, of school shootings like Columbine, Parkland, and Uvalde which threaten physical safety. In addition, striving for emotional safety of students within the context of the racist, ableist, classist, etc. history and current reality of schools does not allow for safety to be achieved. Indeed, the social and political reality of our educational system is that teachers cannot guarantee a safe space, that safety is, at best, an illusion. Put simply, the goal of safe spaces in classrooms, coupled with the reality that schools cannot be safe, is an aporia. In this manuscript, we will highlight that our collaboration engaged in reflexive expertise when we met aporias. In other words, as reflexive expertise is the ‘how’, aporias are the ‘when’.

In the following section, we orient the reader to the context for this manuscript, the three of us as MTEs, and the structure of our research group. After, we present an overview of our work on teaching about culture and its role in the math classroom and the collaborative autoethnographic process we draw upon to analyze conversations of our research, seeking to capture movement through *orientations* as we consider the ethical implications of our work.

Methodology

One of our major contributions to the field is the methodology we employed. We provide the essential elements of this collaborative research project—active positioning (Boveda & Annamma, 2023), iterative research group meetings, friendship as method (Timman-Healy, 2003), and transformative collaborative autoethnography (Chang et. al, 2013)—for those interested in pursuing a similar research path while acknowledging that our methodology was intensely personal, and thus not trivially generalizable. Specific structures, decisions, and working group goals were also important to this work. In this section, we aim to describe and reflect upon these decisions to make our choices and decision-making transparent.

Positioning and Our Group

The three authors are early-career MTEs at two mid-sized public universities in the Southeast and Pacific Northwest. Katie and Rebecca were departmental colleagues and taught the same mathematics education courses at the same institution. They met John in 2021 during a professional fellowship and formed this research project after a series of informal interactions. We are all experienced K-12 teachers and expressed a shared interest in teaching in more culturally relevant and responsive ways as well as supporting our PTs to recognize the importance of culture in mathematics. John taught mathematics content courses, and Katie and Rebecca taught blended content and pedagogy courses for PTs. Our preparation, research backgrounds, and interests are varied (e.g. quantitative, mixed-methods, qualitative experiences and expertise). Our K-12 teaching contexts are also notably different—we have worked in urban and suburban settings in the Midwest and Southern United States; at elementary, middle and high school levels; in schools with different populations with respect to racial and ethnic diversity and homogeneity. We are all White⁴, cisgendered, native English speakers.

We could offer many descriptors of our similarities and differences, but we instead draw on Boveda and Annamma's (2023) call to move from the idea of positionality as a static list of identities or proximity to marginalized communities in favor of the idea of *positioning*. The nature of our weekly meetings, collaborative relationship, and autoethnography allowed for us to consider our positioning as “an active verb where researchers reflect and address where their locations lie in relationship to interlocking systems of oppression; fields of study; and, most importantly, research participants over time.” (p. 2). We take the stance that our positioning is constantly changing as our knowledge and experiences expand. Thus, “we are both determined and determining” (Cousin, 2014, p. 14). For over three years now, we have been engaging in journaling, shared reading, and discussion around our axiology, culture, instructional decisions, and role in upholding or dismantling White supremacy. Our shared experiences meant that in and across our meetings, we often focused on students. Notably, this included our current preservice teachers, but most often included their future students, the children the PTs would someday teach. Our divergent experiences meant we quickly learned to value each other's experiences and expertise, and this most informed our readings, as each of us brought unique perspectives and interests that ultimately informed our collective growth as teacher educators. We saw this research group as a space to explore our shared commitments and go beyond acknowledgement of privilege to leveraging that privilege and power to dismantle inequitable systems and support future teachers to recognize them and take action as well.

This manuscript offers a glimpse into the discussions, tensions, and new insights gained from our critical friendship as it relates to our reflexive expertise. Specifically, the ways in which we navigated unresolvable tensions—aporias—through intellectual flexibility by shifting (consciously and unconsciously) our orientations demonstrated our development of reflexive expertise. In our development as early-career MTEs, we have found ourselves engaging in reflexivity that has allowed for more intentionality in our research and teaching choices, questioning the status quo, our power and privilege, and the harm we and our institutions and society cause. We recognize the urgency and responsibility that we as White scholars have to share our stories of accountability, grief, and complicity, alongside the tension of taking up space in these conversations. We share stories and consider the ways in which our reflexivity, friendship, and love for each other allowed for us to reflect, grow, and change in ways beyond simply the personal, developing expertise as MTEs.

⁴ We have intentionally chosen to capitalize White to avoid affirming Whiteness as the norm (Thúy Nguyễn & Pendleton, 2020).

The Impetus for This Project

Our work as a research team began in December 2021 as we started on a parallel journey of developing curricular units for teaching about culturally relevant mathematics teaching (CRMT) to PTs and engaging in critical self-reflection together through collaborative autoethnography (Chang et al., 2013, Taylor & Coia, 2012, 2020). Over the course of this project, we have taught, reflected upon, and revised several activities focused on supporting PTs in interrogating their own culture and considering the role of culture in the mathematics classroom (*Figure 1*; Bragelman, Rupe, & Borowski, 2022). However, we acknowledge that doing such work well is difficult and requires intensive self-reflection; we did not want to oversimplify culturally relevant teaching (Sleeter, 2012). Thus, as we have developed curricular units, we have also been interrogating our own identities and privileges, often in parallel with the PTs enrolled in our courses. It is important to note that while CRMT is what initially brought us together and is the context for our broader work, it is not the focus of this manuscript. Instead, we focus on how the development of trust, friendship, and love in our collaborative work allowed us to interrogate the challenges we faced and how navigating the aporias we encountered was critical to the development of our reflexive expertise.

Figure 1. Timeline for this research project.

Research Team Meetings

Initially, we began meeting weekly with the sole purpose of creating instructional tasks and units focused on teaching preservice teachers how to teach in culturally relevant and responsive ways and then collecting data on the “effectiveness” of these lessons. However, the focus and nature of these weekly meetings quickly shifted to be more expansive, deeply personal, and intellectually enriching. Because of the complex nature of culturally relevant teaching and our shared commitment to do a “good” job, we often found ourselves questioning each other, interrogating our own beliefs, and looking to scholars for new learning. We surfaced tensions regularly, such as Rebecca’s interest to do no harm, Katie’s interest to provide sufficient nuance, and John’s interest in being subversive. After a month or two of meeting, our weekly meetings began to take a semi-regular structure that cycled through (1) a new shared scholarly reading, (2) sharing and reflecting upon individual journals around a shared prompt, (3) drafting or revising CRMT activities, and (4) reflecting on our implementation of those tasks. For example, one month our weekly meetings focused on: (1) A discussion of Bowers and Lawler’s *Anarchism as a Methodological Foundation in Mathematics Education—a Portrait of Resistance* (2021); (2) sharing and commenting on our journals about our axiology, which came out of reading Bowers and Lawler (2021), (see *Figure 2*); (3) developing equity of voice norms and revising a class survey to

use with our PTs; and (4) reading recording transcripts from a previous meeting for data analysis purposes.

- 1) What are the intrinsic and extrinsic principles that shape our perception and practice?
- 2) Let's write down ideas about principles and then which ones actually shape our practice. Are there any that *don't* inform your practice? Are there values that you try not to take up in your practice?

I put this off until the night before our meeting. But I'm doing it! Because it's important. And trying to articulate these hard things pushes me to be critical, to think, to distill my values. What is at the top of my mind now? How will I see this statement tomorrow? In a week, month, year, etc? I'm going to be thinking about how my axiology may have changed and may have stayed the same.

Figure 2. Snapshot from a shared journal.

Over multiple years, our weekly or biweekly group meetings have been responsive to our interests, academic and professional needs, and personal needs. We each have unique strengths and areas of expertise, which we have encouraged and drawn upon. For example, John is well read across a large number of topics. In our regular discussions, he would often make connections to authors or papers, which Rebecca and Katie would then read after our meetings or suggest as shared future readings. It is also important to make explicit here that we were intentional in connecting to and seeking out scholars of color as we expanded our knowledge based on our interests. We did this for many reasons: to be critical about the politics of knowledge production, to engage with a wide variety of frameworks, and to consider how authors of color might respond to our work, questions, and ideas without requiring the labor of collaborating with us. We also looked for scholars who were centering students' and teachers' humanity in their research about education. Many of the topics which we read were directly related to trying to navigate the aporias we were experiencing. We found ourselves seeking scholarship to help us better understand or try to resolve these unresolvable tensions. In Appendix A we share a chronological, non-exhaustive list of the readings our group engaged with over the course of this project

As we sought to understand and describe what makes our collaboration unique, we read "Friendship as Method" (Tillman-Healy, 2003) which resonated deeply with our group. For us, the weekly research meetings evolved into a regular space where we got to know each other, shared joys and challenges in both our personal and professional lives. As Tillman-Healy puts it, "those who are 'just friends' can be just friends, interpersonal and political allies who seek personal growth, meaningful relationships, and social justice" (p. 731). We found our research goals and developing friendship working in this way. Friendship as method is not simply working with friends; we have all been in research groups with people we recognize as friends. Instead,

Calling for inquiry that is open, multivoiced, and emotionally rich, friendship as method involves the practices, the pace, the contexts, and the ethics of friendship. Researching with the practices of friendship means that although we employ traditional forms of data gathering (e.g., participant observation, systematic note taking, and informal and formal interviewing), our primary procedures are those we use to build and sustain friendship: conversation, everyday involvement, compassion, giving, and vulnerability. (p.734)

Through this methodology, our research team was able to bring our full selves and to engage with our project in ways that centered our humanity and honored flexibility. For example, we set weekly goals and usually had “homework” between meetings. However, we regularly checked in to update each other about our progress towards those goals and events in our lives impacting us, which prompted flexibility, extra support, or adjusted timelines. Our check-ins were met with acceptance and reminders to prioritize family, obligations with more rigid expectations, or self-care. We also considered roles, responsibilities, and workload in ways that were focused on our capacity and strengths versus a goal of equal contribution. There was a regular ebb and flow of who might have been perceived to be leading the work, and we always collaborated openly about what each of us wanted to work on or contribute to the group.

Transformative Collaborative Autoethnography

The choice of collaborative autoethnography as our methodology included a purposeful connection to transformation (Hernandez et al., 2022), which can be a by-product or intentional goal of collaborative autoethnography. This methodology allows us to use personal experiences—our feelings, emotions, and responses to the implementation of culturally relevant teaching practices—as data as we seek to “gain a cultural understanding” (Chang, 2008, p. 49) of ourselves and our students. In choosing autoethnography, we recognize the affordances and ways in which it is unique from self-study, including its attention to the shifting aspects of self and postmodern possibilities, rejecting the notion of a single self with “questions and perspectives gathered to question perceived realities” (Hamilton et al., 2008, p. 22). While some of our initial intentions for sharing ourselves and reflecting together were related to improving our practice, characteristic of self-study, the nature of our discussions and relationship quickly shifted to understanding ourselves in deeply personal ways within the contexts and cultures of academia and White Supremacy (cis-hetero patriarchal, abled, and so forth). While some of us may hold marginalized identities (disabled, queer, femme), in this space, we lean into the ways in which our membership in the dominant culture juxtaposed with our tenure-track early career positions as mathematics teacher educators (and its potential to empower or discourage our agency) require us to make space for honesty. We each have been committed to going beyond acknowledging our privileges to leveraging them to help dismantle the inequitable systems which have given these privileges.

As three junior faculty members, we recognized the benefits of transformative collaborative autoethnography in offering community, solidarity, and support. Within a transformative autoethnography model, there is explicit attention to transformation and a praxis orientation (Hernandez et al., 2022). This can allow for “noticing experiences that create a disorienting dilemma or conflict, critically assessing through self-reflexivity one’s experiences and previous assumptions, [and] applying new practices, skills, and knowledge, potentially replacing old views with new perspectives” (p. 78), among other processes. We also take friendship as an element of our method (Tillmann-Healy, 2003), as our collaboration is deeply informed by our love and care for each other.

Our Data

In collaborative autoethnography, data can include a variety of personal artifacts, such as self-narratives, group interviews, discussions, reflections, and shared narratives, among other things. For us, we have collected recorded (bi)weekly meetings, meeting notes, written personal journals, written comments and responses to each other’s journals, email correspondence, interviews of each other, and shared reading reflections and notes. We specifically focus on and analyze our (bi)weekly meetings as the primary data source. Our data analysis included flexible qualitative

approaches including collaborative meaning making discussions and thematic coding, among other strategies. Our data includes 50 meeting recordings and transcripts collected over 18 months (January 2022-July 2023) and individual journals in which we reflect on the implementation of our curricular units and answer critical and deeply personal questions which have been raised during meetings.

Each of our meetings was recorded, transcribed, and chunked into sections based on the content of the discussions. A typical section was two to five minutes in length, ending when a new point or topic was introduced. We then conducted a macro-review (Chang, 2008) of the data, reading through meeting transcripts, and making notes about themes and important ideas discussed in each section. In the summer of 2023, we identified three meetings which contained particularly compelling ideas and tensions or shifting understandings. As was typical of our meetings, we posed questions to the group to try to better understand ourselves and our work. In this case, we wondered, what may be causing these tensions and how are we navigating them? We reflected upon the data and considered a variety of possibilities. One particularly salient observation was that we seemed to be considering different *orientations*, connected to the idea of paradigms, and zooming in and out (Stinson & Bullock, 2012) in an attempt to understand the aporia we were facing. This led to our decision to analyze our meeting recordings based on the paradigmatic *orientation* we were demonstrating.

After identifying three meetings that contained examples of aporias, we then conducted a micro-review (Chang, 2008) of these meetings. Each of us read the selected meeting transcripts and coded each section for the orientation (process-product, interpretivist, sociocultural, sociopolitical, or spiritual) underlying our thinking. In Table 1, we offer more information about the ways in which we drew from Stinson & Bullock (2012) and Gutiérrez's (2022) descriptions of different paradigmatic moments in mathematics education (process-product, interpretivist, sociocultural, sociopolitical, or spiritual) to describe and understand our orientations towards our work. We use the term *orientation* to both differentiate our own thinking about these paradigmatic moments from the ways in which they have been conceptualized in the literature and to communicate the ways in which orienting oneself is an active intellectual exercise.

We met three times to compare our codes and determine consensus in the event of coding differences. We continued coding individually, with nearly 100% agreement. After determining our initial meeting selections did not contain many codes of spiritual orientations, we coded an additional meeting from the summer of 2023. Through this process of chunking discussions into thematic sections and coding for orientations (Stinson & Bullock, 2012; Gutiérrez, 2022), we were able to identify shifts in orientations, tensions raised in our discussions, and transformations in our ideas and practice. Table 1 is provided to offer examples of how we operationalize the *orientations* we take based on different paradigmatic frameworks. Through examples related to research foci; positioning; and truth, knowledge and values, we intend to show the ways these ideas are distinct from each other.

Shifting Orientations in the Face of Aporias

During the data analysis process, which included revisiting meeting recordings, selecting meetings for further discussion, chunking meetings into thematic sections, macro-analysis discussions to develop a thematic coding scheme, and coding meetings, we often considered what caused us to shift orientations in a particular moment. In our collaborative work we often faced tensions or challenges during meetings; yet these particular meetings under analysis were different. We connected to Lather's (2006) idea of aporias, "impasses, the stuck places of social research across paradigms" (p. 48). We found that in each of these meetings we experienced an aporia and

	Process-Product	Interpretivist	Sociocultural	Sociopolitical	Spiritual
What we say:	When researchers focus on tangible outcomes; data-driven; objective oriented	When researchers are focused on individual interpretations and meaning	When researchers recognize how social, cultural, and individual contexts inform meaning making	When researchers recognize that power, identity and politics shapes meaning making	When researchers focus on goals “aligned with healing ourselves and building ethical futures” and includes their axiology. (Gutiérrez, 2022) Centers collectivist ways of knowing and healing.
Examples in conversations, as in our orientation:	We are focused on outcomes: things like papers, conference presentations, grant funding, coding reconciliation.	We are focused on each other’s perceptions of an event or experience; and we shift towards discussing our lived experiences and how they’re informing our individual perspectives.	We are focused on how our different communities of PTs experience our curriculum differently; we discuss how PTs’ culture and their students’ cultures can inform our work	We are focused on politicized outcomes; as we discuss PT teaching and learning, we are focused on how our work ultimately impacts marginalized groups	We are focused on hope and ways we can take action in alignment with our values and ethics; in our classes, we invite PTs to consider ways math has harmed them and imagine new possibilities for their future classrooms.
Truth, knowledge, values	There is a single Truth that can be discovered through scientific methods.	Every individual has their own truth	Multiple truths that are socially, culturally, and historically informed	Multiple truths, shaped by power and identity; shifting towards post-, there is no truth. Some truths are more valued and accepted by society	Truth as a collective futurity for multiple beings including the earth

Table 1. Connecting our orientations to paradigmatic moments in mathematics education.

used reflexive expertise as a way to navigate these aporias. Holland (1999) offered that different levels of reflexivity can focus on movement “within, across, around, and beyond paradigms” (p. 474). In particular, at the highest level of transdisciplinary reflexivity,

the kind of enlightenment we seek at the end of the pathway to radical reflexivity is not simply another paradigm; it is a way of handling and transcending the interminable debates which have laid down disciplinary and paradigm boundaries. It is an aspect of the elusive postmodernist position, which is not so much a fixed location as a method of evaluating existing systems of knowledge, tied in as they are to sectional interests and constellations of power. It invites re-entry into the epistemological and sectional complexities of our human condition to intervene, "knowingly" according to our ethical priorities. (p. 476)

Our analysis of these meetings allowed us to see ourselves transitioning between different *orientations* as we tried to navigate irresolvable issues—aporias—often reflecting upon power, knowledge production, and our own ethical priorities. In what follows, we offer conversations and analysis that describe the aporias we faced, the *orientations* we adopted in response, and the ways in which we leveraged our reflexive expertise throughout the process.

Findings

In this section, three discussions from our weekly meetings are offered as sites where movement between *orientations* demonstrates our reflexive expertise as MTEs. The conversations include times when we faced aporias and navigated them by shifting *orientations* to approach the impasse. The first aporia we discuss occurred while struggling to code responses about our PTs' conceptions of culture. The aporia required us to question our choices in a novel way, approaching the challenge from different *orientations*. The second and third aporias occurred in the context of highly emotional conversations, considering violence, harm, and the ways in which we are complicit or actively part of the problem. These three aporias illustrate the ways in which we used our reflexive expertise to "expose the underlying assumptions on which [our] arguments and stances are built" (Holland, 1999, p. 467). In the meetings where these conversations took place, we were not consciously adopting different *orientations* to help us resolve these challenges. Nor were we fully aware that the issues we were dealing with collectively were aporias, and therefore irresolvable. For each aporia, we briefly describe the context of the meeting and share the *orientations* we applied using quotes and summaries of important moments during those conversations.

Aporia 1: Negotiating an Aporia while coding PTs' ideas about culture

When we first began developing and implementing activities to teach PTs about culturally relevant pedagogy, we had a goal to measure PTs' learning. How did their thoughts about culture and culturally relevant teaching change after engaging in the activities? To explore this, we approached the question like we had been trained in our doctoral program, through a pre- and post-survey, to measure change over the semester or quarter. After collecting data, we began coding PT responses to our survey questions, adopting a top-down thematic analysis for culture in PTs' responses.

Our initial coding meetings, whether intentionally or not, adopted a clear *process-product orientation* as we tried to quantify the ways in which PTs' ideas about culturally relevant mathematics teaching had changed. During meetings, as we reconciled our coding, questions were raised about whether this approach was helpful or sufficient for making sense of PTs' responses. We shifted multiple times through different orientations. Movement to an *interpretivist orientation* occurred as we focused on understanding PTs' thinking instead of quantifying their learning. Later we considered what we knew about students and our classroom contexts as we shifted to a *sociocultural orientation*. Finally, we showed evidence of a *sociopolitical orientation* as we considered group naming

and the power, privilege, and implications of doing so. In the following section we highlight these paradigmatic shifts in orientation via a conversation that took place on October 10, 2022.

The goal for the meeting from which the following quotes are from was to reconcile our individual coding of PTs' answers to the following questions: *What is culture? How would you describe your culture?* We sought to code PTs' answers as surface, shallow, or deep, using definitions established by Hammond's (2015) Culture Tree (p. 24). Briefly, surface culture refers to observable patterns (e.g. music, holidays, food); shallow culture is related to unspoken rules (e.g. personal space, ways of handling emotions); and deep culture includes the collective unconscious, beliefs and norms (e.g. world view, spirituality). Early in the meeting we determined Responses A and B in *Figure 3* should be coded as "surface".

Response A:	Culture is what people do and how they interact with things and other people. Culture is more how people act.
Response B:	Culture is the different people that are around us. The traditions that people have, their way of life.
Response C:	To me, culture is a community that shares a general approach of doing things, observing things, and overall just having traditions and celebrating a comfortable atmosphere.

Figure 3. PT responses to the question "What is culture?"

Later we began to question our ability to code PTs' responses without imposing our own interpretations of their answers. Consider our discussion about Response C in *Figure 3*.

REBECCA: It could be shallow, but we'd be making a big assumption because they don't say anything more detailed. It could be shallow, it could be surface.

KATIE: So, shallow says, "This level is made up of the unspoken rules around everyday social interactions and norms, such as courtesy, attitude towards elder nature of friendships, concepts of time, personal space, nonverbal communications, and appropriate touching" (Hammond, 2015, p. 22).

JOHN: So this person would have had to say what made it a comfortable atmosphere [to be coded shallow]?

KATIE: I'm wondering if... "culture is a community that shares a general approach of doing things." That's not about traditions.

REBECCA: I see what you're saying. It could be the way of raising your kids...It could be how you prepare your food.

JOHN: The only reason I was leaning towards shallow by the end is that when [the PT] talks about a comfortable atmosphere, I see that as an emotional connection.

REBECCA: Okay. And the tree talks about emotional impact on trust. (Hammond, 2015)

This discussion highlights our struggle to position PTs' conceptions of culture from a top-down approach, through a priori coding, and it highlights the beginning of our shift from a *process-product orientation* to an *interpretivist*. Our orientations during our meeting continued to shift from *process-product* to *interpretivist* and back, as our interpretivist inclinations conflicted with our desire to stay within the process-product moment for the sake of coding.

Response D:	To me, culture is what surrounds you in your life and makes you feel at home. It's your traditions.
Response E:	To me, culture is a collection of thoughts, beliefs, and traditions of a particular group of people.
Response F:	Culture is a broad term to describe the norms, ideas, and customs of a particular area or place.

Figure 4. Additional PT responses to the question “What is culture?”

Upon reading Response D, Rebecca questioned whether “makes you feel at home” was the same thing as comfort and thus should be coded as shallow. John added that the word *home* implies something different than the word *house*. For Response E, we were unsure how to code “beliefs.” John argued that it felt shallow, because “It’s generic. It’s almost too generic.” Despite the culture tree (Hammond, 2015) describing spirituality as deep, we hesitated to code this one word as deep. When analyzing Response F, Katie commented, “I don’t feel like norms and ideas are different things. Can we say that’s deep?” Again we began at a *process-product orientation* and shifted to an *interpretivist* one. Every attempt at reconciling a code led to a discussion of the PTs’ original meanings.

As we attempted to code PTs’ responses to the question *How would you describe your culture?*, new questions arose, specifically regarding how to code a PT’s naming of a cultural group as part of their community membership.

Response G:	My culture is Chinese Vietnamese American. My culture is Asian. My culture is Buddhist.
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Figure 5. PT response to the question “How would you describe your culture?”

Rebecca was unsure how to code Response G, because naming the culture did not “address any of the specifics of that culture.” Katie wondered whether it was unfair to expect PTs to be specific given the nature of our question, commenting, “I could say I’m White... but why would I describe what that means for me from this question?” Rebecca commented, “They are identifying themselves with a group. If they say ‘I’m White’ or ‘I’m Black’ or ‘I’m from Phoenix’ they are identifying part of their identity. But we cannot ascribe value for what that means to them.” We decided naming the communities to which they belonged was in itself significant because of the sociocultural impacts of belonging in such communities. We also brought in context and ideas from our classrooms, illustrating a *sociocultural orientation*.

After deciding group naming to be significant, we coded responses describing their race, ethnicity, or nationality (e.g. Black, Vietnamese American, Latinx) as “deep”. However, we were hesitant to consider a response of “I’m White” as deep, questioning what was implied in this naming. This prompted one of several discussions that pushed us beyond a *sociocultural orientation* into a *sociopolitical orientation*. Rebecca asked, “If somebody says, ‘I’m White and I don’t have any culture,’ are we going to code that deep because they named themselves as White?” John responded, “If someone actually says, ‘I’m White,’ that’s huge in terms of naming your own culture. I think that is deep,” but acknowledged that different people might have “different emotional baggage” around such naming. Katie then asserted that, “passing a value judgment” on what PTs’ cultural memberships mean to them is hard to justify for the sake of a code.

We recognized that our own naming of ourselves as White, in conjunction with our understanding of Whiteness, could be different from a PT naming themselves as White. This question about PTs' culture was not written to allow us to code the various ideas that may have informed their answers. We considered applying a different layer of coding, determining a level of specificity for each response in addition to coding for depth. Yet now in a *sociopolitical orientation*, we questioned whether this coding of PT responses was meaningful in terms of goals for this research. We could continue to wrestle with the ambiguity and utility of a coding scheme that felt "close enough", but ultimately we decided to abandon coding these responses.

The aporia we encountered as we attempted to find a coding scheme to analyze PTs' responses to survey questions resulted in multiple shifts in *orientation* as we struggled to resolve it. Although we began in a *process-product orientation*, we soon realized that our coding scheme was limiting. We could have chosen to stay within this orientation, developing a detailed code book that would allow us to consistently assign a code to every response. Instead, we adopted an *interpretivist orientation* to coding PTs' responses, as we struggled to infer meaning in their responses. We recognized the *sociocultural* and *sociopolitical* impact of membership with a particular group, particularly those who have been historically marginalized or historically privileged. In shifting from *process-product* to *interpretivist*, to *sociocultural*, to *sociopolitical*, we engaged in reflexive expertise, abandoning initial choices for coding in pursuit of a methodology that would align with our values, beliefs, and goals as researchers. We were beginning to accept the messiness and complexity of PTs' responses and were approaching what Childers (2014) calls promiscuous analysis—"an unruly approach to thinking about and engaging with empirical materials that is less interested in doing it 'right' and more interested in flexing, breaking, and blurring theoretical and analytic boundaries as needed to respond to the field" (p. 819).

The tension and resulting shifts in orientation suggest our collaborative was encountering an aporia. The impasse we encountered was the irresolvable interactions between a researcher-scientist's attempt at objectivity, the recognition of the subjective in all facets of the research process, and our seemingly slow acknowledgement that our analytic process must resonate with our values and beliefs as researchers and teachers, our axiologies. From Lather's theorizing (2006), this aporia might be one of objectivity, the tension between the subjective and objective; of complicity, the tension between researcher and researched, or of difference, the tension that arises from categorizing. Rather than forcing the encountered aporia into a category, we leave it unnamed.

Reckoning with Uvalde: Navigating Aporias in the Wake of Tragedy

On May 25, 2022, we met for our regularly scheduled meeting. The day before, 19 children and two teachers were brutally murdered during a mass shooting at Robb Elementary School in Uvalde, Texas. During this meeting, our conversation quickly became very personal, as we considered our own experiences with gun violence and active shooter drills as children, classroom teachers, and teacher educators. Our friendship was very important on this day; we were raw, vulnerable, and honest with each other. Over a year later, as we were analyzing transcripts for this project, we revisited this conversation. We spent two meetings in July 2023 with the goal of coding the transcript from May 25, 2022. Instead, we found ourselves revisiting the topics and themes of our original conversation and reflecting on how our thoughts and feelings had and had not changed in the subsequent year. The transcript from these two July 2023 meetings also became a source of data for this study. For ease of communication, we will refer to the conversation that took place on May 25, 2022, as the "original Uvalde discussion" and the subsequent conversation across two meetings over a year later, as the "follow-up Uvalde discussion." This horrible tragedy forced us to navigate multiple aporias, two of which we share here. Due to the extremely emotional

nature of these particular conversations, we have made careful decisions around whether to quote or summarize our words from those days.

Aporia 2: Navigating an Aporia While Considering Helplessness and Complicity

As we processed the tragedy, we considered whether and how we should address the incident with our education students in classes that week. Our own feelings of anger and helplessness were salient in this conversation. We vacillated between a *sociocultural orientation* when sharing personal stories and processing our own emotions, and a *sociopolitical orientation* when we considered the societal and political factors that have led to the overwhelming prevalence of school shootings. During the follow-up Uvalde discussion, we took a *spiritual orientation*, considering collective trauma and the potential for collective healing. In what follows, we offer moments from our discussion that demonstrate our reflexive expertise.

As experienced educators, we are each very familiar with the fear, anger, and despair that comes with news of school shootings. Now as teacher educators, we grappled with how we should talk about this event with PTs. Rebecca commented, “We’re supposed to talk about culturally relevant teaching and modify [a] task [today in class]. How do you even have that discussion without acknowledging [the school shooting]?” We then collectively negotiated the complexity of engaging PTs in discussion about this event.

KATIE: Yeah. I “took” [uses air quotes] 45 minutes of our class last week, talking about racialized violence in Buffalo⁵ and how you have to be prepared to make space for students and all of that...and it’s just another fucking thing this week. Which I’m going to make time for, of course. It’s just...What are we supposed to do? The only thing that’s different from Sandy Hook⁶ is all our kids have these fucking traumatic drills they do now. That’s the *one* thing.

JOHN: I just, I’m having a hard time...my current emotional state is just apathy. I have no more energy to give you additional emotions. And it’s not that I don’t feel anything, it’s just like...holy shit.

KATIE: There’s no time for that...There are no solutions to any of this shit.

After sharing stories of extreme personal struggles, Rebecca shared how she and her graduate school colleagues navigated extremely difficult challenges.

REBECCA: It’s just like ‘this really sucks, but I just can’t think about how much it sucks.’ So it was, like... we coined it protective apathy. You have to be indifferent to it, because the other option is letting it break you.

Early in the meeting, we shared some of our experiences leading children through active shooter drills and our frustration that the procedures at our schools did not feel like they would actually keep us safe in the event of an active shooter. Rebecca shared her difficulty with dropping her daughter off at school that morning, leading to discussion of parenting young children and worrying they are never truly safe. As we listened to our stories, focused on understanding each other, we took an *interpretivist orientation*. We frequently shifted to a *sociocultural orientation* as we

⁵ On May 14, 2022, a self-described White supremacist killed 10 Black people at Tops supermarket in Buffalo, New York.

⁶ On December 14, 2012, 20 students and six staff members at Sandy Hook Elementary School in Newton, Connecticut were murdered. At the time, this mass school shooting elevated the topic of gun control in the United States.

discussed our experiences as K-12 teachers and considered the ways in which our contexts were noteworthy. As we considered the ways in which the media, politicians, our school systems, and broader American culture were continuing to normalize school shootings instead of addressing any of the root causes (i.e. violent patriarchy, White supremacy, poverty, and capitalism), we took a *sociopolitical orientation*.

This *sociopolitical orientation* was increasingly present as we reckoned with our anger about living in a society that allows such incidents to happen. John wondered about the lack of communal spaces, commenting, “If you want to harm a community, you [seem to] have two options: church or school.” He also commented on mental health, “I feel like we’ve become much more progressive with mental health and then something like this happens.” Rebecca was critical of the mental health narrative that often emerges in the media after school shootings, arguing, “I don’t think it’s about mental illness. I think it’s about White supremacy and violence and toxic masculinity. Every time the narrative comes out, they [politicians, the media] want to talk about mental illness because it turns the attention away from guns.” Katie shared, “I just keep coming back to capitalism and neoliberalism and all of that. What do we even do?”

Despite our years of teaching experience, commitment to ongoing learning and professional growth, and tendency to face difficult issues head on, we were at a loss of how to respond to this horrific event. As tenure-track professors, we have power, privilege and expertise, especially in the eyes of the PTs in our courses. We anticipated that our PTs would be seeking solutions, expecting us to have some answers. As we continued to reckon with what to say, we vacillated between the *sociopolitical* and the *sociocultural*, sharing experiences and context from our own lives that have informed the way we think about these issues. Considering our positioning, we recognized that our power and privilege (directly intertwined with Whiteness) mattered in these conversations. What is normalized and what is hidden in these discussions with students? Because of the work we had been doing together and with PTs, we felt like we could not address this event with them without acknowledging that fact. We had talked amongst each other and with students in our classes about Whiteness and White culture. In this meeting, in our vulnerability with each other, one of us shared:

ANONYMIZED: I think I finally articulated what White culture was for me. And it was really hard to type out because I wrote it in the first person. And I was just staring at it at the end of writing it. And I was like...I think this is accurate. I don't think I'm lying...Essentially in my post I said that White culture is inhumanity. It's essentially cultural appropriation. Like when someone's like, 'what song is White culture?' Well any song is White culture, because if I want it, it's mine. Any food is my culture, because if I want it, it's mine. Anything—it's mine. I take it, and then I dip it in hand sanitizer and mayonnaise and it becomes mine. And...it's true. That's what [my culture] is. It's jazz. It's hip hop. It's tacos. It's fucking P.F. Chang's. It's everything. And writing it out...like, that process of normalizing. And then, at the same time that process of *abnormalizing*.

White culture (and White supremacy) is also school shootings. It's violence. It's disconnecting communities and emphasizing individualism. The duality of normalizing and *abnormalizing* these ideas through naming and critiquing them was at the top of our mind here. The conversation continued and Katie wondered, “How do we support preservice teachers in starting to think about these things in a way that feels not completely overwhelming? Not completely undoable or... [Our students are] struggling, you know. They're living through this shit, too.”

We also traversed *orientations* in the follow-up Uvalde discussion. Taking a *sociocultural orientation*, John shared that “It takes a lot to talk about healing immediately after a violent act.” Katie took on a *sociopolitical orientation* when she commented, “There’s attention to mental health as a real important concern and [also] being used as an excuse, a crutch, a connection to White supremacy.” We wondered why we didn’t find any evidence of a *spiritual orientation* during the original Uvalde discussion and questioned whether it would have been possible to take such orientation so soon after the tragedy. Katie commented that a spiritual turn (Gutiérrez, 2022) towards healing doesn’t ignore the wound, and perhaps the empathy and emotional work we provided each other while sharing our stories could be considered spiritual.

JOHN: When I was reading [the transcript of our Uvalde conversation], I was thinking at the time... We didn't get to talk about it...but I really wanted the conversation to shift away from harm into healing. And it's something I've been thinking a lot about since we had this conversation. Because we're working with future teachers. How do you create a community that's more resilient against fostering the kind of harm that produces school shooters? And I know that's putting a lot on teachers, but I think talking about it at the community level is important.

REBECCA: While we were analyzing this, we were thinking about...one of the tenors of this conversation is ‘What the fuck do we do?’ Right? And what you just said, John, is a potential thing that we could do. How we do that...it's a completely different discussion. But that's something that was missing when we had the conversation the first time. I think that we're seeing this now in a different way.

In the context of these comments, Katie shared that teaching was healing for her, later adding, “What I can give to preservice teachers is space for them to imagine something different than their own experiences. So it feels to me like teaching and learning is a healing space.” We had learned a lot since May 25, 2022. The reading we had done about reflexivity, positioning, harm, and paradigms allowed us to see this conversation differently. It was reflexivity in practice.

Unlike the first *aporia* we experienced while coding data where we moved across orientations from a *process-product orientation* to, ultimately, a *sociopolitical orientation*, in the Uvalde discussions, we vacillated between *orientations*, spending considerable time between a *sociocultural orientation* and a *sociopolitical orientation*, also shifting to an *interpretivist orientation* as we processed our personal perspectives on the tragic event and its meaning for our individual work moving forward. In reflecting upon our feelings, ideas, and growth since the initial conversation, we also shifted to a *spiritual orientation*, explicitly centering our friendship and love for each other—“embrac[ing] socioemotional learning and care for each other” (Gutiérrez, 2022, p. 380). The nature of this conversation included deeply personal stories and vulnerability in sharing our fears and hopelessness, unlike the more common task of coding data. Yet, in both of these conversations, we found ourselves asking questions and pushing for clarification from each other that were representative of different paradigmatic orientations, allowing for our reflexive expertise to develop.

In the wake of the Uvalde shooting, we worked together to navigate an *aporia*. In many ways, we have been taught that research should be objective—unemotional. Yet in the context of preparing teachers, the violence of the profession (e.g. overt violence such as school shootings, and systemic violence such as the prison to school pipeline) evokes emotion. As MTEs, we support preservice teachers not just in content or pedagogical knowledge development but also preparation to enter a profession. Mathematics content and methods courses are contextualized in the

profession, which means we are responsible for preparing PTs to negotiate teaching math in professional contexts. This conversation and the analysis that followed allowed us to understand this aporia in new ways.

Aporia 3: Navigating an Aporia while Considering the Illusion of Safe Spaces

Over our years working together, we have often discussed the potential harm that may arise from our curriculum on culturally relevant teaching, particularly for those PTs who are members of historically marginalized groups. We recognize that schools have been and continue to be sites of inequity by enacting policies such as tracking and zero tolerance (Berry, 2018; Berry et al., 2013; Martin, 2009, 2019). In our work to train culturally responsive teachers, we have struggled to find ways to encourage PTs to interrogate their privilege while also honoring their lived experiences. As experienced K-12 teachers, we recognize the tentative nature of positive classroom environments, understanding that our choices can have both positive and negative impacts, as can students' interpersonal relationships. These conversations again demonstrate our reflexive expertise, shifting between various *orientations—interpretivist, sociocultural, sociopolitical, and spiritual*.

During our Uvalde discussions, we reckoned with the notion of “safe spaces” as we confronted the reality that no classroom is truly safe.

JOHN: If your goal as an educator is to create a safe space and classroom, that's almost impossible.

KATIE: ...You can't say your class is a safe space. It's not. You can try to do as much as you can to make it as safe as possible. But putting up this goal of it's going to be safe here is thinking you're in control of something that you're not. I've been just trying to call it a culture of respect...Everyone is going to make a mistake. I'm sure I've hurt some of your feelings that I'm aware of and some that I'm not aware of. And so there's no way I can say that it's safe here. I can make it safer. I can raise our consciousness of how our actions and words and choices impact how we feel in our classroom. But it feels like the “safe space”... it's [only]... for people [with privilege]. Like we want to feel like we're being fine and neutral and safe and everyone can feel good here. But that's not acknowledging the complexity of race, culture...

In this conversation we confronted the complex sociopolitical realities of our world, especially our education systems. For Rebecca, the resolution to do no harm had been a significant tenet of her teaching philosophy for many years. We recognized that many of the culturally relevant activities we implemented could both encourage White PTs to interrogate hidden, assumed myths (such as meritocracy) and potentially harm PTs from marginalized groups for whom such lessons brought up negative experiences (such as hearing microaggressions from their peers). Rebecca expressed a desire not to harm such PTs but began to wonder about the implications of her view (Martin, 2006). We collectively wondered, was safety an illusion? Or, if we were providing some measure of safety, for whom?

While notions of violence, harm, and safe spaces were particularly salient in our Uvalde discussions, they came up for us at other times, too. In a meeting on January 17, 2023, we troubled our individual views about harm as we shifted to an *interpretivist orientation*. John mentioned that he is motivated by a desire “to do harm to systems of oppression.” Rebecca was initially surprised by this framing, because of her inclination to recoil from harm. As John explained his perspective, Rebecca critiqued it in contrast to her own, and Katie found parallels between the two positions.

KATIE: And I wonder...it feels to me like the commonality between what the two of you are saying is this idea of confrontation. Like, bringing things to students to confront? I don't know...Because so much of refining your thinking is just acknowledging that there are other ways to think, right? You're so enculturated to whatever *it* is...Fill in the blank. Then you read, you experience, you go somewhere. Something happens that fundamentally offers you a different way of thinking or being. And so I wonder if it's the mode in which you are thinking about getting students to that point.

In this conversation we coded instances where we shifted between an *interpretivist orientation*, as we attempted to understand each other's perspectives, and a *sociocultural orientation*, as we attempted to understand how our individual social contexts influenced our shared perspectives. As our discussion turned to how our desire to do harm or avoid it influenced our work as teachers and researchers, we shifted into a *sociopolitical orientation*. We struggled to determine whether our beliefs, values, and goals as MTEs were either in harmony or tension. For Rebecca, was her action—recoiling from violence—a product of embracing caring, or was it a product of protecting a system that ultimately supports those with privilege? For John, was the desire to do harm to a system of oppression ultimately still reifying that system of oppression by embracing violence? As the discussion continued, John commented that harming systems of oppression wouldn't necessarily require violence, to which Rebecca countered, "Isn't harm always inherently violent?" Rebecca shared her belief that violence begets violence and her fear that if a bad system is destroyed through violence, whatever replaces it would also be inherently violent. Katie interjected that the inequity of our current school system is already violent, commenting, "[So many] children have already been met with violence. So, what's the difference? The difference is at least the system is starting to change or come apart."

As the conversation continued, it became clear that we were at an impasse. Katie suggested that harm and violence exist on a spectrum—perhaps we should not think about them as all or nothing. John questioned whether his desire to do harm to systems of oppression would prevent him from taking a *spiritual* turn. Our conversation shifted again, hesitantly moving towards a *spiritual orientation*, yet with resistance as we explored the tensions of violence, hope, and healing. In this conversation, our reflexive expertise pushed us to take seemingly simple notions—do no harm, classrooms should be safe spaces—and deeply interrogate the assumptions surrounding those notions, first as individuals and then as a group.

As we continued to discuss these ideas in future meetings, we increasingly took a *spiritual orientation*. Rereading Gutiérrez's paper about a spiritual turn in mathematics education (2022) pushed our thinking and allowed us to see our work and our past conversations through a different lens.

JOHN: My take was that it is so easy to adopt a deficit perspective or a harm-based perspective or a trauma-based perspective that it takes a deliberate, intentional focus on desire-based to shift the field away from that trauma focus.

KATIE: Yeah...I found what I was looking for... (reads an extended quote from Gutiérrez's paper) "Where is the evidence that we have wondered alongside of our participants and that we are answerable and reliable to them, that we are engaging in axiological work? What if every researcher needed to express not only the longings and desires that propelled them to design and carry out research in that way...Our research not only implicates us, it has the potential to liberate and heal us." (2022, p. 385) ...I think positionality statements are important. I also feel like there's something more interesting to why I make my decisions,

and why I think about teaching in the way I do than my positionality. And I recognize that my positionality is a piece of it. But I feel like I've just thought about it in such a more expansive way. And so, this idea of centering "How did we come to this work. Why are we choosing these designs?"...like that feels more revealing than what I think the intention of a positionality statement is...or at least what it has become.

We often talked about how the space we had made for each other to be honest, reflective, and moved to action was a space of healing. In the face of our field's dominant (although shifting) way of viewing teachers and students, teaching and learning with a deficit or trauma-based gaze, we found our group to be a space to trouble these ideas and affirm our unwavering asset-based views of students and teachers. Through our collaborative friendship, we made space for each other to share our axiologies, question each other's words, and interrogate the ways in which we upheld the status quo or lived our axiologies. In developing our expertise as MTEs, we found the movement to healing, a *spiritual orientation*, to be important. By confronting our aporia related to safety, we were able to acknowledge that safety is an illusion, yet we will still all strive to create spaces where people can bring their full selves. By shifting our *orientations*, employing our expertise, we were able to find a way forward in the face of this aporia.

Discussion

In this manuscript, we offer reflexive expertise as one way to conceptualize MTE expertise. Holland's (1999) conception of reflexivity, of movement between and potentially transcendence of paradigms informed the ways in which we faced irresolvable tensions. Using transformative collaborative autoethnography (Chang et al., 2013), positioning (Boveda & Annamma, 2023), and friendship as method (Tillman-Healy, 2003), along with *orientations* derived from the historical paradigmatic context of mathematics education (e.g. Stinson & Bullock, 2012; Gutiérrez, 2022), we analyzed recordings of our research team meetings to identify instances where we shifted *orientations* multiple times in a meeting. Identifying such shifts as reflexive expertise, we posited that multiple shifts in *orientations* were prompted by aporias (Lather, 2006). This project has shown reflexive expertise as a potentially necessary component of teaching culturally relevant teaching. Reflexive expertise can surface aporias, making the hidden visible (Bullock, 2018). Connected to these ideas, we offer a potential rationale for *why* we shift *orientations* as MTEs and researchers.

Our reflexivity became more pronounced and identifiable during conversations where we negotiated aporias, "stuck places of social research across paradigms" (Lather, 2006, p. 48). We posit that our shifting of perspectives, *orientations*, was motivated by our desire to resolve these aporias. The conversations shared in our findings reckon with aporias of coding objectively vs. interpretively, helplessness vs. action in the face of violence, and the goal vs. impossibility of creating safe spaces in classrooms, particularly in discussions of equity and culturally relevant teaching. In each case, we took an *interpretivist orientation*, trying to understand our personal assumptions and perspectives on the biases that may be hidden. We then engaged with the aporia as a group, questioning assumptions and exploring our understanding and perspectives. In other words, as we met an impasse, an aporia, our perspectives shifted as we negotiated the implications of the aporia for our work. Indeed, the notion of aporias resonates with the unforeseen dangers of racial or cultural biases Milner (2007) warns against or the epistemological and ontological biases Scheurich and Young (1997) caution against. Our reflexive expertise allowed us to accept the lack of resolution in each of these conversations. Previously, we may have believed that the lack of resolution to each of these ideas would have indicated failure or a lack of understanding. Reflexivity, however, allows us to understand these aporias do not have clear resolutions. Expertise

does not mean that we find answers to all of the problems we encounter as researchers and MTEs. Instead, our reflexive expertise allows us to better navigate the tensions we encounter even though they remain unresolved. We are better able to navigate the unresolvable.

Beyond recognizing and navigating aporias, we suggest that this ongoing research project has another critical offering to the field. In our roles as MTEs, we are in an ongoing process of utilizing and developing a wide range of knowledge and skills. We argue that we would not have been able to engage with these aporias deeply in just *any* research group. *This* group, *this* research collective allowed us to grow professionally and personally in countless ways. But, why? What makes this group different? Our friendship and love for each other must be acknowledged as a centerpiece of our collaborative relationship. In our work together, we sought to find ways to support each other in taking action against the myriad of ways injustice exists in teacher preparation programs, K-12 schooling, and society. Over time, we found “those who are ‘just friends’ can become *just* friends, interpersonal and political allies who seek personal growth, meaningful relationships, and social justice” (emphasis in the original; Tillman-Healy, 2003, p. 731). We were each early-career scholars, seeking connection and support, and our relationship made our research stronger.

As we described in the methods, our group elevated each other’s strengths (both personal and scholarly) and organically created systems that allowed us to explore our shared and unique interests. One such system was choosing readings based on our group’s axiological and methodological needs in response to aporias we were negotiating, rather than choosing, for example, recent research in our field of study. In an attempt to extend our understanding of positioning, we sought to learn from scholars in other fields, scholars of color, and other voices that expanded our personal understandings. Reflecting through journal writing and regular collaborative meetings, without an emphasis on research products (e.g. How does our work together lead to new publications?), helped us develop reflexive expertise. We offer these details to acknowledge that the work to teach in culturally relevant ways, including fighting inequity and oppression in our local university contexts and beyond, takes time and care. In many ways, our collective was fundamentally in opposition to the culture of academia—which values publications, grant money, etc.—while imposing and upholding racist, classist, sexist, and ableist systems and structures. As early career scholars, this research group gave us space and support to navigate these systems and stay true to our values.

Reflexive expertise developed over time together in this research group led to deeper understanding of the nuances surrounding the aporias we faced and negotiated by shifting *orientations*, allowing us to make informed decisions built upon that expertise—without needing a clear resolution in order to take action. This focus on movement directly parallels Boveda and Annamma’s (2023) argument regarding positioning versus positionality. Naming our salient identities or proximity to research participants does not acknowledge the fluid and context-specific ways in which MTEs’ identities and experiences influence their research and teaching (Boveda & Annamma, 2023; Herbel-Eisenmann et al., 2015). Positioning is active and takes time, especially since many were never taught how to do this work (Waitholler, 2023). Aporias have the potential to illuminate additional ways in which positioning as a verb versus positionality as static is valuable; reflection on the intentional repositioning of one’s perspective as a researcher and their reflexive expertise offers one way to make visible the hidden tensions in our work (Bullock, 2018). We posit that movement across paradigms is a natural progression of Boveda and Annamma’s (2023) troubling of researcher positionality. As we shifted our *orientations*, we regularly considered our positioning within those moments. Rather than identifying our positionality at the beginning of that work and remaining static in that decision, we allowed for flexibility, seeing how our contexts, power, and identities shifted organically across the various aporias and contexts we encountered.

The types of research questions we were asking, the way we analyzed data, and the goals we set for ourselves individually and collectively were more intentional through our collaborative autoethnography work.

Reflexive expertise and movement between paradigmatic *orientations* provides an opportunity for MTEs to continue reckoning with the sociopolitical in their teaching and begin to make the spiritual turn called for by Gutiérrez (2022). Considering when and how we shift *orientations* allows for continued interrogation of the interactions between knowledge, power, and identity that are characteristic of the sociopolitical turn (Gutiérrez, 2013). Reconceptualizing expertise as the ability to shift *orientations*, both in teaching and in research, can offer perspectives on ways common tensions in our work as MTEs can be negotiated. In our work, the aporias we encountered were most frequently related to the challenges of culturally relevant teaching. Yet we do not believe this is the only topic around which developing reflexive expertise is meaningful and important. Rather, the development of reflexive expertise, especially through the navigation of aporias, has potential for improving the work of all MTEs, and even the work of researchers and educators beyond mathematics education. Further, it allows for a transition into the spiritual, looking for unity and healing as we consider the roles our minds, bodies, contexts, and power play in our work (Gutiérrez, 2022).

Conclusion

We consider the work done through this collaborative autoethnographic project to be transformative. Making ourselves the focus of study allowed us to deeply interrogate our beliefs, motivations, and goals. As White teacher educators teaching PTs about culturally relevant mathematics teaching, we consistently attempt to understand the ways our privilege and the myths of White supremacy may be influencing our ideologies and beliefs. Collaborative autoethnography allowed us to surface and interrogate aporias in a way that would not have been possible without each other and without an intense analysis of the data collected through this project. The “integration of multiple researchers/participants” in the investigation of our reflexive expertise led to “transformative benefits” (Hernandez et al., 2022, p. 68). We are better teachers and researchers, not only because of our reflexive expertise, but also because of what we have learned about ourselves through this research. Hernandez et al. (2022) emphasize “the utility and efficacy of the transformative element of autoethnography has not been fully realized,” (p. 72) and we highly encourage our colleagues in mathematics teacher education and beyond to adopt collaborative autoethnography as a potential methodology for studying their own practice and selves, to consider more promiscuous methods and methodologies (Childers, 2014) in the face of aporias.

Critical consciousness cannot be developed alone. As a group of White scholars, we developed a deep friendship and utilized collaborative autoethnography to inform our methodology, allowing us opportunities to include emotion and embodied ways of knowing (Estola & Elbaz-Luwisch, 2010; Klein & Taylor, 2023), and hopefully expand what knowledge in research is valued. There are opportunities for healing and fluidity in understanding our stories, “so we encounter our autobiographies not as fixed entities but rather as texts that encourage a re-reexamination, re-living, dialogue, and inquiry” (Coia & Taylor, 2002, p. 149). Reexamining our experiences—growing up, as K-12 teachers, as current MTEs—has led to transformation. Surfacing aporias and utilizing reflexive expertise as we attempted to navigate them has made us more aware and deliberate MTEs and researchers.

Afterword

This paper has been in the works for a long time. The deep love we have for each other has been a constant over the past four years and has informed all aspects of this paper. Perhaps because of the complex and deeply personal nature of our collaborative research group, we have had a hard time trying to capture our work in a research article format. Past iterations have been submitted to other mathematics education journals where the question “Where is the math?” has been a central criticism. Unwilling to rewrite a previous version of this paper to fit neatly into a typical mathematics education journal, we revisited our data and tried to really answer the question, *why has this group been so powerful for us?* Each of us have grown personally and professionally through this group. When we read Lather (2007) together, revisited from grad school for John and Rebecca and new to Katie, the idea of aporias finally helped us name an important aspect of our work together. We didn’t move past or ignore the irresolvable tensions we faced in our work and personal lives – we sat with them. We troubled them, interrogating assumptions and perspectives we held as individuals and as a group (researchers, teachers, teacher educators, friends, activists). We looked to scholars, authors, and artists to help us consider new perspectives. We acknowledged that while we may have faced an aporia, we also needed to take actions and make decisions.

Engaging in the open review process shaped our paper in countless ways. Beyond simply open review, the process of publishing this article with JTM-ME has been extremely humanizing and affirming. To state it simply, this paper wouldn’t exist – or certainly not in any form close to this current article – without the generosity of time and mentorship from our open reviewer, Dr. Greg Larnell, and the JTM-ME editorial team. Additionally, we have been supported and inspired by so many brilliant scholars and colleagues who have pushed our thinking individually and collectively throughout the past several years. An ever-present tension in writing this paper has been navigating the space we occupy as White people. Publishing our work takes up space in the limited (but growing) arena for academic publishing. We have sought critical feedback from scholars of color and hoped to gain new insights into what we are doing and trying to say – while also recognizing all the ways in which Whiteness steals labor and does not value the unseen labor of mentorship and feedback.

While reading, citing, and using frameworks of scholars of color has been a constant in our research group, we also saw open review as an opportunity to collaborate with a colleague who we knew would push our thinking and share honest feedback. To our knowledge, this was also Greg’s first time engaging with the open review process. His first feedback to us was in writing and he prepared a reviewer letter that synthesized his feedback (much like a traditional reviewer might do). After processing his feedback together, the three of us met with him twice over the course of about a year, with many emails shared between meetings. He was extremely supportive of our ideas and encouraged us to be more explicit about our contribution, the language we used, and to freely use ideas and frameworks in new ways that connected to what we were experiencing together. His insightful questions and suggestions can be seen throughout the paper. The process was not transactional or bound by a rigid deadline, but rather, was focused on creating the best paper we could.

Situated in the reality that White people need to be doing anti-racist work, especially in the White and female dominated K-12 education field, we also need to create models for collaboration. We don’t want to be in an echo-chamber. We need to be vocally pushing back against systems (working exactly as they are intended to work). We share this afterword without (too much) fear of judgement. Because speaking about this dialectic tension (an aporia perhaps) is needed to continue to do this work.

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Appendix A: Chronological List of Readings from Our Collaborative Research Project

- Milner, R. H. (2007). Race, culture, and researcher positionality: Working through dangers seen, unseen, and unforeseen. *Educational Researcher*, 36(7), 388-400. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0013189X07309471>
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